

Research Article

SING Your Way to a Better Biology

Farah Kautsar Binti Kamal Basya^{1, *}, and Nazmi Harith-Fadzilah²

¹ Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Jalan Parit, Tanjung Belanja, 32800 Parit, Perak; farahkautsar@mara.gov.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-6974-3513>)

² The Microbiome Lab (TML), Universiti Malaysia Pahang Al-Sultan Abdullah, Lebuhr Persiaran Tun Khalil Yaakob, 26300, Gambang, Pahang, Malaysia; nazmiharith@gmail.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2472-1630>)

* Correspondence: farahkautsar@mara.gov.my

Abstract: *Biology students often struggle with Latin terminology, process sequencing, and conceptual application. This study proposes the SING technique- Syllable Meaning, Integrated Gesture, Netizen Skill, and Guided Reflection which is a multimodal strategy designed to improve biology learning among IGCSE and SPM students. Implemented from 2023 to 2024 the results showed a statistically significant performance in subject grade average difference in IGCSE with 0.48 and in SPM with 1.48. Pre- and post-test comparisons validated effectiveness. From the verbal feedbacks students recall facts quicker, started to incorporate more visualisation in their studies, think critically to solve problem and overall being more confident. Future work will explore integrating SING with educational technologies to further enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.*

Keywords: gesture; critical thinking; pedagogy; metacognition; secondary school; syllable.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Biology students often struggle with understanding of Latin terminology. Students often find it hard to grasp the meaning of the scientific term hence facing difficulty in explaining the related concept (Husna et al., 2023). Moreover, remembering the sequence of complex biological processes has also been a challenge to them which could be attributed to poor memory retention and lack of technique used. Furthermore, students also struggle to scaffold on pre-requisite knowledge let alone applying the concept learned in a specific context to solve problems (Husna et al., 2023).

Several pedagogy methods have been explored to enhancing students' understanding of the fundamentals within biology topics, information retention and critical evaluation of the taught facts. For example, the Latin terms were broken down into parts and are understood individually (Poupova, 2018). Another method is to incorporate physical gestures during memorisation, to reinforce memory retention (Musaeus & Musaeus, 2021). Inculcating critical thinking process when exploring topics by bolstering student participation in the classroom improved students' biology academic performance and cognitive ability (Ristanto et al., 2020). Furthermore, implementing teacher guided reflection in classroom promotes students' self-assessment and metacognition ability Ristanto et al., 2020).

These methods demonstrated success in student's performance in varying degrees, but may not overcome the challenges in learning biology comprehensively. Incorporation of all the pedagogies above may work synergistically and comprehensively addressed the shortcomings of each method individually. We coined the term SING which is an abbreviation of the following:

S - Syllable Meaning: Break down Latin terms to learn word parts (Poupova, 2018).4

I - Integrated Gesture: Use gestures to reinforce learning processes.(Musaeus & Musaeus, 2021)

N - Netizen Skill: Encourage collaboration and peer feedback.(Ristanto et al., 2020)

G - Guided Reflection: Promote self-assessment and metacognition. Ristanto et al., 2020)

The aim of this study is to demonstrate and evaluate the SING technique on the learning outcome of the biology topics among secondary school students.

2. METHODS

2.1 Class Setup

The study was carried out in two form 4 classes (401 and 404) with 47 students who were the candidates of International General Certificate of Secondary Education (IGCSE) 2023. The exposure to the SING technique continues on two form 5 classes (501 and 504) with 48 students who were the candidates of Sijil Pelajaran Malaysia (SPM) 2024.

2.2 SING Intervention Steps

The testing period was between the end of 2022 to 2024. The SING technique was implemented on the same cohort of students beginning in Form 4 and continuing through Form 5 students. The pre-test data was collected from paper 2 multiple choice marks in Final Semester II examination results conducted in October to November 2022. Students were exposed to SING technique from April to July 2023. Post-test data was collected from paper 2 multiple choice marks in Mock IGCSE (International General Certificate of Secondary Education) examination conducted in August to September 2023 to assess the efficacy of the technique. The total marks for both pre- and post-tests paper 2 were 40. Higher marks signify better academic performance.

The second set of pre-test data was taken from Standardized test results on paper 1 multiple choice questions conducted in April 2024. Students were exposed to SING technique from May to September 2024. Post-test data was collected from the trial SPM (Sijil Pelajaran Malaysia) examination carried out from October to November 2024 to evaluate the efficacy of the technique. The total marks for both pre- and post-tests paper 2 were 40. Higher marks signify better academic performance.

Subject grade average (SGA) data was collected from 2019 cohorts of IGCSE and SPM examinations. The data was then compared with the respective data from cohorts of 2023 IGCSE and 2024 SPM examinations. Lower SGA signifies a better academic performance. Prior cohorts did not receive exposure to the SING approach, and students from 2020 to 2022 were excluded from the study due to disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The demonstration of the technique is available online (<https://youtu.be/HcPMRFGJXoQ>).

2.3 Statistical Analysis

Microsoft Excel was used for statistical analysis. Student's *t*-test was used to perform statistical test between groups of data.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 SING Intervention in Mock IGCSE and Mock SPM

The incorporation of SING technique showed statistically significant difference in both form 4 classes with 2.83 marks average difference (Figure 1a). For the Form 5 students, the class 504 showed significant improvement in marks but the students from class 501 had no significant improvement.

Figure 1. Comparison before and after SING technique exposure in two different mock examinations. (a) IGCSE (b) SPM.

3.2 SING Intervention On SPM Performance

The cohorts of 2023 IGCSE and 2024 SPM candidates who were taught the SING method had a very significant improvement in SGA compared to the 2019 who had no prior exposure. The 2023 IGCSE cohort had 0.48 lower SGA difference (Figure 2a), whereas the 2024 SPM cohort had an even more significant 1.4 SGA difference.

Figure 2. Comparison before and after technique exposure in two different high stakes examinations. (a) IGCSE (b) SPM.

4. DISCUSSION

The SING technique which incorporates, breaking down terminologies, incorporating gestures and visuals, encouraging critical thinking and self-assessments had demonstrated strong positive impact on students' biology subject performance through a more significant examination scores.

Furthermore, through personal communication with students, we have learned that students were able to recall facts quicker, enjoyed practicing gestures and using visualisations in their notes and memorisation. In addition, we also observed more frequent instances of higher cognitive abilities among students where they asked and discussed more critically among their peers and teachers. However, the practice of SING technique may not be comprehensive due to several external factors such as students' participation in outside classroom activities which may have interfered with the process of inculcating SING techniques among students.

5. CONCLUSION

The SING technique provides a multimodal approach which significantly improves biology students' performance in IGCSE & SPM respectively. Integrating gestures, collaboration, vocabulary skills, and reflection fosters better comprehension and notable success in high stake examinations. We would like to explore technology integration of SING technique in future.

Acknowledgments: This study is supported by Maktab Rendah Sains MARA Parit, Perak.

References

- Husna, H., Nerita, S., & Safitri, E. (2023). Analysis of student difficulties in learning biology. *Journal of Biology Education Research (JBER)*, 4(1), 1–8. <https://journal.unpak.ac.id/index.php/jber>
- Musaeus, L. H., & Musaeus, P. (2021). Computing and Gestures in High School Biology Education. *Annual Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education, ITiCSE, June*, 533–539. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3430665.3456307>
- Poupova, J. (2018). Biological terminology: an opportunity for teaching in tandem. *International Conference New Perspectives in Science Education, 1960*, 382–385.
- Ristante, R. H., Djamahar, R., Heryanti, E., & Ichsan, I. Z. (2020). Enhancing students' biology-critical thinking skill through CIRC-based scientific approach (CIRSA). *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(4 A), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.081801>